

COMMUNICATION CHALLENGES AND THE MOST ESSENTIAL LEARNING COMPETENCIES IN WRITING AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to test the perception of the students towards their communication challenges in terms of personal, psychological, and technical factors and to gauge the level of students' competence based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in writing namely, Argumentation and Logic, Writing Patterns and Development, Writing Processes and Properties and, Writing Correspondence and Channels of Communication. Furthermore, this paper targeted to correlate the perceived communication challenges and the level of writing competence as independent and dependent variables, respectively. Using descriptive method of research, it involved 120 Senior High School students of Calamba City Science Integrated School during the DepEd's Learning Continuity Plan amidst global pandemic, School Year 2020–2021. A 30-item modified standardized survey questionnaire was utilized to elicit the respondents' perception on communication challenges in writing. Meanwhile, to determine the level of writing competence, 35-item Writing Competence Exam was administered. Using mean-frequency scale and Pearson's correlation coefficient, results revealed that the respondents have no considerable communication challenges in writing in terms of personal, psychological, and technical factors. Moreover, the study also showed that they are in 'Approaching Proficiency' in terms of Argumentation and Logic, 'Developing' in Writing Patterns and Development, and Writing Correspondence and Utilizing Channels of Communication, and 'Proficient' in terms of Writing Processes and Properties. Meanwhile, it was concluded that the null hypothesis is accepted – there was no significant relationship between the perceived communication challenges and their writing competence level. Finally, it can be inferred that there are other factors which affects their performance outside the writing challenges which were tested. These external factors may be motivation, learning styles, teachers' pedagogy, delayed and minimal feedbacks, distance education limitations and challenges, and varying learning modalities.

Keywords: communication challenges, writing competence, most essential learning competencies